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OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Маткаримов Алишер Исмоилович

СПОРТ МАЖМУАЛАРИНИ ЛОЙИХАЛАШ ВА ҚУРИШ ПРИНЦИПЛАРИ

DRJI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

2023-2024

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

